

LARGE-SCALE GRAPH VISUALISATION OF OPEN WEB INDEX AND ITS EVOLUTION IN TIME*

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Abstract

Dynamic networks are models that describe the evolving relationships between real-world entities in various application domains such as social network analysis, communication, biological processes, or the Internet. Web networks are a special type of information network where nodes represent web pages, each other connected by hyperlinks.

Visualisation of complex networks is a key tool for their analysis and interpretation. The graphical representation allows intuitive recognition of structures such as communities, central nodes, or important connections between parts of the network. Well-designed visualisations make it easier to navigate the data, but also support understanding of dynamic changes in the network and enable effective presentation of results.

Visualisation and processing of (extreme) large-scale networks is challenging due to unique characteristics such as load imbalance, lack of locality, and access irregularity. Considering the possibilities offered by recent supercomputing power, we have revised current algorithms suitable for the visualisation of large-scale networks and were able to visualise networks in sizes ranging from hundreds of thousands to million nodes. The experiments were performed on the visualisation of the Open Web Index produced by the OpenWebSearch.eu project. The complexity of the problem is discussed in the context of performance and computation power needed for the visualisation of such (extreme) large-scale graphs.

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